

MIDDLE EASTERN RESPIRATORY SYNDROME: A BRIEF REVIEW

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ABSTRACT The Middle East respiratory syndrome is a zoonotic viral disease caused by a novel Coronavirus named Middle East Respiratory Syndrome-Coronavirus (MERS-CoV). More than 1806 cases have been reported in human beings till the end of 2016 with a fatality rate of more than 30%. Majority of the cases have been reported from Saudi Arabia. Many healthcare-associated outbreaks have been reported with the most significant such outbreak being reported from the Republic of Korea in 2015, where 186 cases including 36 deaths occurred. MERS is a viral pneumonia with rapidly progressive respiratory failure leading to ARDS. It presented a wide range of clinical manifestations and associated with significant mortality rates in hospital admitted patients with comorbidities. Multiple surveillance and phylogenetic studies suggest a bat origin for this virus. A diagnostic real-time reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) is done to detect MERS-CoV. Supportive treatment is the mainstay of management as no specific drug treatment exists for MERS. Resveratrol has shown to inhibit MERS-CoV infection and prolong cellular survival after virus infection. It is also inhibited by interferon type I in cultured cells. Adequate infection control measures are the mainstay in the management of MERS-CoV. Surveillance should be conducted on a large scale among humans and different animal species to determine the exact rate of spread of MERS-CoV.

KEYWORDS Coronavirus, Pneumonia, Resveratrol

1. INTRODUCTION

In June 2012, a new coronavirus was isolated from a male patient in Saudi Arabia who was suffering from severe respiratory illness & later died in a hospital in Jeddah. This virus was initially named as human coronavirus-EMC and later named as Middle East Respiratory Syndrome-Coronavirus (MERS-CoV) (1). MERS-CoV is known to cause severe hypoxemic respiratory failure with multi-organ failure and often requires admission to the intensive care unit (ICU) (2). Since June 2012, multiple outbreaks have been reported in or been epidemiologically linked to the Arabian Peninsula [1]. Till 27 September 2016, there were

1806 laboratory-confirmed cases reported by the World Health Organization (WHO), which includes 643 related deaths. The majority of MERS cases are reported from Saudi Arabia [2]. The continuous MERS epidemic in the Arabian peninsula is believed to be related to the failure to control the zoonotic sources. Many healthcare-associated outbreaks have been reported with the most extensive such outbreak being reported from the Republic of Korea in 2015, where 186 cases including 36 deaths occurred. The index case had a travel history to Arabian peninsula [3].

2. GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRIBUTION

MERS cases have been reported from 27 countries which include few from European, Asian, North American and African continent. Majority of the cases have been reported from the endemic region of MERS which is the Middle East. Recent reports of MERS case from Korea indicated the rapid spreading potential of this virus & not checked by early detection and infection control measures [4]. After Saudi Arabia, Korea has the second highest number of MERS cases (n=185) and United Arab

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Emirates (UAE) in third with 83 cases. There are at least 13 cases of MERS reported from UAE, Jordan, Philippines, Malaysia, Algeria, Egypt, Greece, Netherlands, Qatar, United States and Turkey which were reported to be spread via travellers who visited Saudi Arabia [4]. Travel related MERS cases have also been reported from the United Kingdom, Italy, France, Germany, Tunisia & Iran [5]. Patients reported outside the middle east, all had a history of travel to the middle east or had contact with a primary case [6].

3. VIROLOGY

Coronaviruses are large enveloped single-stranded RNA viruses [7]. The glycoprotein spikes surrounding the spherical virion give the viruses its characteristic "halo appearance" on electron microscopy [5]. Coronaviruses can infect and cause disease in many animal species including bats, mice, birds, dogs, pigs and cattle [7].

Human coronaviruses belong to two genera: Alpha coronaviruses and Beta coronaviruses. The genus Beta coronaviruses consist of 4 lineages, A, B, C and D. Severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS-CoV) belongs to lineage B, but MERS-CoV belongs to lineage C beta coronaviruses. Sequence analysis shows that MERS-CoV is closely related to the bat coronaviruses HKU4 and HKU5. Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) was also derived from bat coronaviruses. MERS-CoV has a similar phylogeny and is considered a cousin of SARS-CoV but both have distinct biology, such as the use of different human receptors. [8,9].

Since the discovery, various names have been attributed to MERS-CoV like human coronavirus – Erasmus medical centre (hCoV-EMC), human beta coronavirus 2c England Qatar, human beta coronavirus 2c Jordan N3, beta coronavirus England 1 and novel coronaviruses (NCoV). Currently, the international committee on Taxonomy and the coronaviruses study group (CSG) has decided the name to be Middle East Respiratory Syndrome-Corona Virus (MERS-CoV) [8].

4. VIRAL GENOME AND PROTEIN

The genome structure of MERS-CoV is similar to that of other coronaviruses. The RNAs are capped and polyadenylated with the 5' two-thirds of the genome encoding the non-structural proteins (NSPs) involved in viral replication and the remaining 3' third of the genome encoding the structural genes. The surface of virion has a heavily glycosylated, petal shaped, large protein known as spike (S) glycoproteins [8].

Dipeptidyl peptidase 4 (DPP4) is also called CD26 is a 766-aa type II transmembrane glycoprotein that has been shown to be the functional receptor for MERS-CoV in permissive cell lines [8]. MERS-CoV can bind to DPP4 from several species. In addition to humans and camels non-human primates, rabbits, goats, sheep, and horses, among other animals, are thought to be susceptible to infection [6]. DPP4 is expressed on the cell surface in the lungs, kidneys, small intestine, liver, parotid gland, spleen, testes, prostate and activated leucocytes. This explains the capacity of MERS-CoV to infect cells of these organs. MERS-CoV can also bind to bat DPP4 [8].

5. EPIDEMIOLOGY

MERS-CoV is considered as the second coronavirus after SARS-CoV that can cause a pandemic [4]. Like many other coronaviruses, MERS-CoV is believed to be originated from bats. This

is based on the isolation of other lineage C beta-coronaviruses that are very closely related to MERS-CoV on phylogenetic analysis. However, still, it is difficult to prove that bats are the direct source of human disease [1]. Several other animal species like dromedary camels (*Camelus dromedarius*), cows, goats and sheep have been assessed for serological evidence of MERS-CoV infection. MERS-CoV specific antibodies were only found in dromedary camels. The first detection of MERS-CoV was reported in dromedary camels on a farm in Qatar that had been linked to human cases of the disease. [6,1,10].

The investigation has revealed that dromedary camels are so for the only reservoir of MERS-CoV [11]. Adult dromedary camels have almost 100% seropositivity against MERS-CoV while the virus is found mainly in dromedary calves. In contrast to human infection, MERS-CoV causes no or mild disease in dromedaries [11,6]. Evidence in literature shows that there is a possibility of transition from camels to human & camels are the only confirmed zoonotic source for human infection [6,12,13]. MERS is a zoonotic viral disease that can be transmitted from dromedaries to human beings in which it causes severe respiratory disease with a high case fatality [11]. Seroprevalence of MERS-CoV antibodies was significantly higher in camel-exposed individuals than in the general population [14]. Epidemiological and genomic studies of cases associated with hospital and household MERS outbreaks have confirmed human to human transmission with a high risk of infection seen in patients with immunosuppression or coexisting illnesses. [6,15,16,17]. The rate of secondary transmission among household contacts of the patient with MERS-CoV has been approximately 5% [15].

Regarding seasonality, it was previously hypothesized from the high incidence of cases during spring and early summer months, and this has been postulated that this may be correlated to the camel birthing pattern; young newborn camels are encountering MERS-CoV for the first time may get ill and transmit the virus to humans. However, this hypothesis was nullified after outbreaks of MERS were spotted in the latter half of 2015 & early 2016 in other seasons. An international analysis of the difference in outcomes for MERS cases has shown different fatality rates based on location. African & Middle East countries showed a MERS fatality rate of 41% whereas in Europe it was 47% & Asian countries showed an atypical 20.3% case fatality [4].

A. CASE DEFINITION

The case definition for confirmed and suspected cases have been defined by WHO, the US centres for disease control and prevention and the ministry of health (MOH) of Saudi Arabia [6]. A confirmed case is defined as any person with laboratory confirmation of MERS – CoV infection based on positive real-time polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) of MERS – CoV in swab samples collected by MOH in addition to any one of the following clinical definitions: Fever (>38 C), a cough, shortness of breath (SOB). A sore throat, vomiting, diarrhoea, hemoptysis, chest pain and infection, respiratory failure, loss of consciousness, runny nose, and any asymptomatic outpatients with a history of contact with positive symptomatic cases are tested positive [12].

B. IMMUNITY, PATHOGENESIS AND PATHOLOGY

MERS-CoV primarily infects the human respiratory tract. It can effectively replicate in the airway epithelium of humans.

Pulmonary endothelial cells are also highly susceptible to MERS-CoV. Human epithelial cells are stimulated to produce antiviral and pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokine to eliminate the invading pathogens. MERS-CoV infection failed to elicit strong pro-inflammatory cytokines response in human primary respiratory epithelial cells and ex vivo respiratory tissues. The virus has evolved multiple antagonistic mechanisms to dampen or attenuate the host defence which contributed to the high pathogenicity in humans [3]. Type I interferon (IFN) expression is a crucial component of this initial response and coronaviruses have developed strategies to prevent IFN induction. Type I IFN activates immune antiviral effectors such as natural killer (NK) cells, T CD8+ cells and macrophages, allowing viral clearance [18]. There is evidence to suggest consistent responsiveness of interferon treatment in vitro for MERS-COV [12].

The human immune cells that are involved in MERS-CoV infection are macrophages, dendritic cells and T lymphocytes [3]. In contrast to the inability to elicit the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines in human respiratory epithelial cells, MERS-CoV can stimulate the induction of pro-inflammatory cytokines/chemokine in human macrophages and dendritic cells [3]. MERS-CoV is characterized by their different patterns of disease; Sporadic cases, interfamilial transmission and healthcare-associated infection [19]. There is also evidence to suggest the extrapulmonary organ involvement upon MERS-CoV infection. MERS-CoV viral RNA could be detected in blood, urine and stool specimens of some MERS patients suggesting viral dissemination. MERS causes an acute highly lethal pneumonia. Renal dysfunction or failure is common in patients [3]. The pathogenetic understanding comes from studies of experimentally infected animals. Studies have used several animals like macaques, marmosets and camels. Infected marmosets develop severe interstitial pneumonia and are a useful model to study severe MERS, but their unavailability limits their utility. Neutrophil and macrophage infiltration and alveolar oedema have been reported from affected lung tissue [6]. MERS mouse models have been generated by prior transduction of adenoviral vector expressing human DPP4. In the MERS-CoV permissible animal models, viral RNA can be detected from multiple organs of the infected animals. However, there was a failure in the recovery of the virus in most extrapulmonary organs [3].

C. CLINICAL FEATURES

The clinical manifestations of MERS-CoV infection range from asymptomatic infection to severe pneumonia with acute respiratory distress syndrome, septic shock, and multi-organ failure resulting in death [6].

Common symptoms at presentation include fever with or without chills and rigour, cough, shortness of breath and myalgia. Gastrointestinal symptoms are also frequent which includes diarrhoea, vomiting and abdominal pain [20]. The median incubation period for a human to human transmission is approximately five days [5]. Two patients from France presented with similar clinical features which included fever, chills, and myalgia. Respiratory symptoms with a cough and dyspnea soon became the predominant clinical symptoms. Both the patients were required ICU admission [7].

Patients needing ICU admission usually presented with fever, abdominal pain, sore throat and fatigue. Crackles, tachycardia and rhonchi were the most commonly identified initial physical signs. Bilateral pulmonary infiltrates lobar infiltrates also reported [21]. Among the pediatric age group, the MERS-CoV

infection rate is low [19]. There is little data available regarding the effect and the likelihood of MERS-CoV in pregnancy. Eight cases have been reported, and the outcome was favourable in the majority of cases [19]. The Risk factors for severity of disease are an immune compromised state, comorbidities like obesity, diabetes, cardiac disease and lung disease [6]. Severe cases of MERS-CoV infection have tended to be recorded in older patients with underlying conditions, while milder cases have been recorded in younger persons [19].

D. LABORATORY DIAGNOSIS

Lower respiratory tract specimen such as bronchoalveolar lavage fluid, sputum and tracheal aspirates contain the highest viral loads, and hence they should be collected whenever possible for viral detection [6]. Real diagnostic time reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) is done to detect MERS-CoV [8].

Laboratory findings of MERS include Leucopenia, particularly lymphopenia, high creatinine, lactate dehydrogenase and liver enzyme concentrations [6]. A single positive target can also confirm the presence of viral nucleic acid with the sequencing of a second positive PCR product [6]. In MERS cases confirmed by PCR, serial sampling for PCR testing from the upper and lower respiratory tracts and another body part (e.g. Serum, urine & stool) are recommended to understand viral replication kinetics and to guide infection control. Genotype sequencing based assays for both the RNA dependent RNA polymerase gene (RdRp) and the N gene has also been developed. A simplified and biological safe protocol for the detection of antibody response by immunofluorescence microscopy has been developed using the convalescent patient serum. Report of a highly specific assay for the detection of antibodies against MERS-CoV using protein microarray technology has also been developed [8]. For confirmation of infection by antibody detection, the paired serum sample should be collected 14-21 days apart with the first taken during the first week of illness. A positive screening assay (ELISA, immune fluorescence assay) should be followed by a confirmatory (neutralization) assay. It is advisable that serological result should be carefully interpreted because they might be confounded by cross-reactivity against other coronaviruses [6]. A monoclonal antibody (MAb)-based capture Elisa for MERS-CoV nucleocapsid protein (NP) detection which is an antigen detection Elisa has been reported [22].

Another detection method is by using reverse transcription – loop-mediated isothermal amplification (RT-LAMP), which requires only a single temperature for amplification and can be completed in less than 1 hour [8].

E. TREATMENT

There are no guidelines on the treatment of MERS-CoV infection. Treatment with Interferon- α 2b (IFN- α 2b) and ribavirin significantly improves survival 14 days after the diagnosis of MERS-CoV infection whereas another study of 5 patients diagnosed later in the course of disease did not show any benefit [23]. Supportive treatment is the mainstay of management as no specific drug treatment exists for MERS. MERS-CoV is inhibited by interferon type I in cultured cells. Several drugs inhibit MERS-COV in cell culture, like cyclosporine and mycophenolic acid [6]. The usefulness of these drugs in a patient is unknown and needs further research. Combined therapy using ribavirin and IFN- α 2b should be further evaluated as it has shown to reduce clinical outcomes in MERS-CoV infected rhesus macaques

[8]. Resveratrol in another drug which has shown to inhibit MERS-CoV infection and prolonged cellular survival after virus infection [24].

F. PREVENTION & INFECTION CONTROL

The Saudi ministry of health (MOH), WHO and the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention have recommended preventive measures against MERS-CoV. The main prevention and control measures are droplet precautions, by wearing a surgical mask within 1 meter of patients and contact precautions which can be taken by wearing gown and gloves on entering patients rooms and removing them on leaving. Eye protection to be used by health care workers treating & monitoring the patient. Personal protective equipment such as gowns, gloves, eye protection and special N95 masks are recommended [6].

If any patient has been exposed to a potential or known MERS case, travel should be avoided. Infection control aspect of MERS has to do with preventing MERS exposures and minimizing person to person spread [5]. Without the ability to prevent community infection, prevention of health care transition will remain a challenge [16].

CONCLUSION

MERS is zoonotic which is transmitted to a human from infected dromedary camels. MERS-CoV is closely related to bat viruses with an unknown reservoir. The origin of MERS-CoV might have been in bats and transmitted to dromedary camels at the same point of time in the past. The transmission of MERS-CoV to humans needs further studies to clarify the role of any amplifying hosts or whether the virus transmitted from bats to camels & then to humans. Large scale serological screening of human populations in areas of MERS-CoV endemicity in dromedary camels should be considered. Surveillance should be conducted on a large scale among humans and different animal species to determine the exact rate of spread of MERS-CoV. Epidemiological research for the deployment of new therapies and vaccines are essential for both human and camels. In the absence of a vaccine or specific treatment, prevention of viral transition through adequate infection control methods is the mainstay in the management of MERS-CoV outbreaks.

COMPETING INTERESTS

This manuscript maintains no competing financial interest declaration from any person or organization and no conflict of interest involved in the outcomes of the finding.

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